

TEACHING AND IMPROVING VOCABULARY THROUGH GAMES.

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Annotation: English is an international language used by a lot of people in the world. It also has a role as a means to learn about science and technology in facing globalization era. Any sources of science using English as their language, so if people do not master English well, any difficulties will be found. Beside that, this language can increase social life with many native speakers who speak it as a foreign language. By mastering this language, the number of misunderstanding of communication with others can be reduced. As the main stipulation of globalization era, English is the key to realize the success of personality, society, and nationality. In this article we will give information about teaching vocabulary through games.

Key words: games, young learners, psychology of games

Recognition of the meaning making potential of words mean that vocabulary became a learning objective in its own right. In his book *Vocabulary and Language Teaching*, McCarthy says, "Vocabulary is the biggest component of any language. If you do not know enough vocabulary you will not be able to express yourself adequately." (1990:2). According to the book of *How to Teach Vocabulary*, Thornburry (2002:13) explains, "Without grammar very little can be conveyed, without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed". Allen (1983), in her book entitled *Techniques in Teaching Vocabulary* says, "Students who do not learn grammar along with vocabulary will not be able to use the language for communication". This means that vocabulary is also important besides grammar. Both grammar and vocabulary are needed in communication. We can make a conclusion that vocabulary is the basic component of language learning, because without understand vocabulary they will have difficulties in the next learning process. To express something, they must know about many words, so that it is easier for them to show what they mean.

D.2. Vocabulary Teaching to Young Learners Teaching vocabulary

to young learners is different from teaching to adults. In her book entitled *An Introduction to Teaching English to Children*, Susan House (1997) says, “.....then by trying to understand better how children learn we will have more understanding on how to teach them”. Paul Fletcher and Michael Garman (1986:210) on their book *Language Acquisition*, say, “Children learn new language from what they hear and they use their ability to imitate a sound of a word from the adult”. Learners learn a new word by listening people saying and try to practice it. They try to understand a meaning of word by producing the same sound like what they have heard from adult. To teach vocabulary to young learners, the teachers have to learn first about the way young learners learn and decide how to teach them. E. Games In his book entitled *Elementary Vocabulary Games*, Hadfield (1998:4) says, “A game is or activity with rules, a goal, and element of fun, which is divided into two kinds; competitive games, in which players or teams race to be the first to reach the goal, and cooperative games, in which players or teams work together towards a common goal”. The book of *Game for Language Learning New Edition* arranged by Andrew Wright, David Betteridge and Michael Buckby (1997:211), stated that there are at least 13 types of game, they are:

a. **Picture Games.** Here the use of picture plays a major part. Broadly, they involve comparing and contrasting pictures, considering differences or similarities; considering possible relationships between pictures such as narrative sequences and describing key feature. It is hoped that someone may identify them or represent them in similar way.

b. **Psychology of Games.** It consists of variety of games, which might all lead to a greater awareness of the working of the human mind and senses. This is an area of interest for each person, in which there are much individual variations of opinion and experience. It encourages concentration and language use.

c. **Magic Tricks.** Language can sometimes be exemplified in a concise and memorable way through magic tricks. From the point of the language learning, this

is marvelous. Magic always attracts attention and invites comments. There is a potentially large occurrence of other languages-the hidden language of the game.

d. Caring and Sharing Games. This game demands and encourages trust and interest in others. There are some difficulties in overcoming the learner's shyness or reluctance to share personal feelings and experiences with other class members. As a result, their problems in learning will be known after they have a discussion with their friends.

e. Card and Board Games. These games have included of adaptations of several well-known and wellbred card games and board games. Snakes and ladders and happy families are the examples of these games. A map game (search) is included and also an adaptation of a gift game (present, and rewards and punishments).

f. Story Games. Story games, by their nature, provide a work for learners to speak and write at length instead of engaging in short exchanges. It is necessary to correct certain errors, and then makes a written or mental note of the errors during the story telling. In order to make the story long, the students should interrupt during the story-telling process done.

g. Sound Games. Sound effects can create in the listener's mind an impression of people, places, and action. There is a demand for the listeners to contribute through the imagination. This inevitably leads to individual interpretations, and individual interpretations lead to a need to exchange points of view and to express opinions and ideas.

h. Word Games. These games are initially focused on the word rather than the sentence such as spelling game (as, for example, in Dash it and Hang it), meaning game (as in Definitions or The odd man out) words for sentence-making game (as in A-B, B-B or Make a sentence).

Used literatures:

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